

OPEN ACCESS TO RESEARCH DATA

Horizon 2020: Open Research Data Pilot

= a requirement to develop a **Data Management Plan (DMP)** and to **enable open access and reuse of research data** generated by Horizon 2020 projects, if it is possible. You can **opt out** of the Pilot for multiple reasons, for example, if participation would mean that the project's main aim might not be achieved, or if participation is incompatible with rules on protecting personal data. More information about the opt-out option can be found in the [General Annex L Horizon 2020 – Work Programme 2018-2020](#).

HOW TO FULFIL THE ORD OBLIGATION?

Step 1: Develop a Data Management Plan (DMP)

- ⑧ A document that specifies what data will be generated during the research, and how it will be handled during and after the project
- ⑧ Deliverable within the **first 6 months** of the project
- ⑧ DMP should be updated as the project evolves and the final version should reflect what actually happened with the data

Step 2: Enable Open Access to the research data

- Ⓐ Types of data covered in ORD Pilot
 - **Underlying data** and related **metadata** – data which are needed to validate the published results
 - Any **other data** (and related metadata), which you decide to publish and specify in your DMP (e.g., raw data, data not directly attributable to a publication)
 - Participating in the ORD Pilot does not necessarily mean opening up all your research data (details should be provided in the DMP)
- Ⓐ Deposit the research data in a research data repository
 - Participants must deposit their data in a **research data repository**
 - A suitable data repository can be found for example at [re3data](#)
 - If you cannot find a suitable repository, you can upload your data to [Zenodo](#)
 - Ideally, you should attach a suitable license to your data (e.g., [Creative Commons](#))
 - Ensure that third parties can **freely access**, mine, exploit, reproduce and disseminate your data
- Ⓐ Provide information about tools
 - Provide information about the **tools** available that are needed to validate the results (e.g., specialised software or code) and if possible, provide the tools themselves via a repository

€ Financing

Costs related to the implementation of ORD Pilot are eligible during the duration of the grant.

More information on data management and DMP requirements can be found in the [Guidelines on FAIR data management in H2020](#), on the [European Commission website](#), or on the [Central Library website](#). You may also contact the [Faculty](#) or [Central](#) Open Access Support.

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